

SPEECH CULTURE AND LITERARY LANGUAGE NORMS

Nazirjonova Zebogul Nodirjon kizi,
teacher, Andijan State University

Abstract: The norm is the state and possibility of application in the speech process of language units adopted, approved and understandable by members of society.

In the system of language and speech, the norm has its own role. From the moment when language began to serve as a material in the process of speech, its normalization became the need for society, and regulatory problems were put on the agenda.

Key words: norm, normative manifestations, spelling, stress, pronunciation, punctuation, lexical, grammatical, methodological, normative in word categories, rules of connection of words, management, adaptation, graduation, word order, speech deficits – defects in oral and written speech, varvarisms, dialectisms, vulgarisms, jargonisms, orthographic and punctuation violation of norms.

With the development of society, the need for the study, analysis of normative States in language and speech has also intensified, and in solving these problems, a number of factors such as the domestic, spiritual and educational marriage of the people, the socio-philosophical and aesthetic worldview, customs were taken into account. It was also not possible to take into account the national characteristics of the language again when researching linguistic phenomena, its normative aspects.

So the norm acquires the content of nationalism and historicism, acquires a tradition that has been formed for several hundred, thousands of years. The fact that traditional norms in the use of language change and update over periods is also a historical process.

It is understood that solving the problems of language normalization becomes

an integral part of the development of each national language culture. Therefore, it is not for nothing that matters of the norm are studied within the framework of the culture of speech

Unfortunately, there is no way to solve regulatory problems in the language, difficulties in short periods of time. If we said the opposite, there could have been an opinion that contradicted the laws of the practice of our language, our real social life today. Let's remember one historical case. In 1989, we welcomed with great joy the law adopted" on the state language of the Republic of Uzbekistan " and enthusiastically entered into its implementation. But it was not possible to fulfill all his substances at once and at speed. While not legal at the time, the fact that the current language of office was Russian, that a part was carried out in Russian by the conditions of people of Uzbek nationality, and involved their children in the education of this language in kindergartens and schools was one of the natural obstacles. As a result, the existing traditions in the use of the Russian language in the process of dealing for a certain period of time, in the maintenance of official business papers, in the holding of conferences of various levels, maintained their strength. To be honest, we have not been able to get rid of these defects in more than fourteen years. We also observe that many of the difficulties in using the Uzbek language have been overcome, and issues related to language practice are being resolved in stages. The process of using language over the past time, Harqalay proved one thing - it turned out that the positive solution of language regulatory problems also depends on the judge who said time.

The Bringing of language elements to a certain norm, on the one hand, is guided by language specialists, and on the other hand, it also occurs naturally. But, in our opinion, one thing is known - the pressure on the states of the language being in practice cannot be exerted. But it is necessary to provide appropriate instructions, instructions, recommendations.

But our work for the culture of the Uzbek language and speech is not at the

level of requirements. To positively solve these tasks, we must seriously deal with the practical aspect of setting the norm of literary language. So what is the practical aspect of setting a norm? As a result of studies and observations, it is analyzed what meaningful and formative possibilities exist in the elements of the Language, linguistic possibilities are revealed, and ways to use them in the speech process are recommended. In a certain sense, it is also a statement that they set the norm and make recommendations regarding the use of language units.

In this context, language professionals, intellectuals can give their correct advice, recommendations, be passionate about it. There are also many positive aspects to this, of course. But the decisive sentence is said by users of this language. On top of that, a certain amount of time will also have to pass until the norm of each language element is established.

Popularization of writing and speaking on the basis of spelling and pronunciation rules among our people, strengthening these rules in the form of dictionaries, setting the norms of language use in each area, including in the field of law, remains one of the urgent tasks of today. Among these, the issue of further elevating the speech culture of our people is also important. Because the idea of national independence aims to make our compatriots an active participant in the process of spiritual renewal and reform, and to teach our youth to think freely, in a new way, this cannot be achieved without language culture.

Although the normalization of language units, bringing them into one form that is common and understandable to everyone is considered the task of linguistics in general, it does not deny the services of the sphere of speech culture. Consequently, the problems of the norm always remain the object of research of this area. The culture of speech theoretically justifies the conditions, laws of application of language units in speech, which are presented in a certain norm in the language, and also controls the observance of this norm in a certain sense. Achievements and shortcomings in speech are analyzed, showing the most

favorable ways to end these shortcomings. "Speech culture makes it a task for itself to introduce a wide-ranging language education and mass stylistic literacy, in other words, the current achievements of language science among the speaker and writer public" [5].

In a continuous process, such as the normalization of language elements, the struggle between old age and novelty always continues. Words and phrases that live in the language do not easily displace new ones that come in their place. A certain period of time can make them live equally, in parallel, and free up space until Times pass.

In the process of the struggle between the same old age and novelty, and the selection of normative manifestations in the language in this struggle, a literary language is formed. The Uzbek national literary language, although it has evolved from the universal language, differs in some aspects from the dialects and dialects present in it, from jargons, from ordinary colloquial language, from the folk language as a whole. Because the universal language contains all the elements found in the Uzbek language and is in an unprocessed form. The literary language, on the other hand, chooses from it options that are understandable and convenient to use for the Uzbek nation, and recommends them as a norm for representatives of the nation.

Although in all manifestations of the universal language, in all linguistic communities there are norms that apply in their own way codified, that is, norms included in certain rules are only a characteristic of the literary language. "Only in literary language," says V.A. Iskovich, - how to speak and how not to speak; recorded in normative grammars, dictionaries, reference books; the rules and guidelines learned in schools apply"6. Therefore, the opposite side of the literary language from the general language is the strict observance of the unified norm in it.

Although the real creator, creator of the language is considered a people, in its

development it is necessary to note the services of our scientists, poets and writers, State and public figures, lawyers, educators and press workers, masters of film, theater arts and publishing houses and journalists. Especially at the time of independence, the services of our linguistic scientists, poets-writers and journalists became great. Due to their effective work, strict standards were established in most areas of linguistics, sample variants of language units in the writing and treatment process were recommended, taking into account new rules and decisions on the development of our native language, many controversial issues in the language system were put on its theoretical basis.

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